

The Ibero-American Indicators of Sport and Physical Activity for Sustainable Development

Country Report of Chile

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This Country Report is the result of intense collaborative work between Chile's Ministry of Sport (MINDEP) and the international cooperation consortium comprising the Ibero-American Sports Council (CID), UNESCO, the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ), the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF), and the Research Centre in Sports Science of the King Juan Carlos University (CIDE).

The consortium especially wishes to express its gratitude to the Division of Sport Policy and Management of Chile's Ministry of Sport, whose technical team was deeply involved and committed to developing this document.

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Introduction

By mandate of the High Authorities of Sport in Ibero-America, including Ministers, the Ibero-American Sports Council (CID), UNESCO, and the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ), have developed the first common indicators to measure the impact of sport and physical activity on sustainable development in Ibero-America. More recently, the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF) and the Research Centre in Sports Science of the King Juan Carlos University have also joined the Consortium.

The Ibero-American sports indicators aim to provide countries with periodic, standardized, and comparable information on the impact of sport across different dimensions of sustainable development. They also facilitate the periodic evaluation of policies to identify opportunities for improvement and support achievements and results. Additionally, these indicators seek to measure the social return on investment in sport, ultimately promoting increased funding for sport and physical activity.

At the XXIX General Assembly of the CID in Cartagena, Colombia, in May 2023, the unanimous approval was given for the creation of 12 indicators and four key data points to be implemented across the region. Furthermore, it was agreed to conduct a pilot implementation of these indicators in a group of applicant countries between August 2023 and March 2024. The countries participating in this first phase of the pilot were Chile, Costa Rica, and Ecuador.

The pilot aimed to validate the relevance and applicability of the indicators for scaling them across the region. It also sought to perform an initial calculation of the indicators based on available data sources and, from there, generate a country report on their status, along with a cross-cutting report on results and lessons learned.

This document corresponds to Chile's Country Report, analyzing the status of the indicators, the scope of the data sources, and the challenges in generating them in line with the country's social, cultural, and economic context. It also establishes their connection with national policies and programs for sport and physical activity.

The Country Report is complemented by technical sheets for the indicators whose values could be calculated during the pilot, as well as a general manual for the development of technical sheets for indicators that could not be estimated. These technical sheets provide a detailed description of the main characteristics of each indicator, facilitating their correct interpretation, implementation, and scalability. They are essential for replicating their calculation and fostering discussion among experts.

Additionally, it is recommended to consult the Pilot Results and Lessons Learned Report, which provides an overview of progress, presents the technical assessment of the indicators by participating countries, and includes a list of lessons learned and recommendations for the next phases of the pilot and the regional implementation of the indicators.

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I. Country Context

Sport and physical activity observed in countries are closely related to their social, cultural, and economic context, as well as the visions and priorities reflected in their policies and strategic programs for the sector. Therefore, to better understand the situation of the indicators, it is important to provide specific country information that allows for a more precise identification of where the main challenges and opportunities lie in consolidating a common set of indicators for the Ibero-American region.

Chile is characterized by having a vast territorial extension, 4,270 km from north to south (Government of Chile, 2024), which implies significant geographical differences within the country and in the ways of organizing and social culture of the communities. This leads to a wide variety of situations and challenges for physical activity and sports.

The population of Chile in 2019 was 19,107,216 inhabitants (National Institute of Statistics, 2023, p. 8), and unlike the regional average, it is characterized by a more pronounced aging population trend. It is estimated that by 2050, there will be 176 people aged 64 and over for every 100 people under 15 years old (National Institute of Statistics, 2023). This implies that, looking ahead, Chile will need to improve its sports and physical activity policies focused on older adults.

On the other hand, given its high level of economic development compared to other countries in the region, Chile has become a country with a high flow of migrants. According to the National Institute of Statistics (INE, 2023), between 2018 and 2022, the presence of foreign nationals in the country increased by 25%. It is estimated that there were 1,625,074 immigrants living in Chile in 2022, with 70% coming from Latin America (INE, 2023). The Venezuelan population stands out, representing 32.8% of the immigrants in 2022 (a 55.6% increase between 2018 and 2022), followed by immigrants from Peru (15.4%) and Colombia (11.7%). These flows influence the cultural composition of the country, which in turn shapes new preferences and ways of practicing physical activity and sports.

Regarding State Administration, Chile is a unitary and democratic state (Art. 3° and 4°, Political Constitution of Chile). The government and administration of the State are the responsibility of the President of the Republic. Additionally, "the Ministers of State are the direct and immediate collaborators of the President of the Republic in the government and administration of the State" (Art. 33°, Political Constitution of Chile). Currently, there are 24 Ministries (Government of Chile, 2024), one of which is the Ministry of Sport.

The country is divided into 16 regions, each of which is administered by a Regional Government with its own assets and budget. Additionally, in each of these regions, there is a Presidential Delegate, appointed by the central government. This Delegate oversees internal government tasks in the region, according to the instructions given by the President of the Republic, and coordinates and supervises the decentralized public services at the regional level (Law No. 19.175). The regions are further divided into 56 provinces, which are administered by a Provincial Delegate appointed by the central government. These delegates are responsible for carrying out internal government tasks in the provinces, supervising development programs and projects executed by public services in the provinces, and implementing coordination measures for provincial development (Law No. 19.175).

The smallest territorial administrative unit in the country is the communes (346), which are managed through Municipalities (one per commune), autonomous corporations with public law and their own assets, whose purpose is to meet the needs of the local community. Their functions include the preparation, approval, and modification of the communal development plan, the promotion of

community development, and the preparation, approval, modification, and execution of the municipal budget, among others (Law No. 18,695). The highest authority of the Municipalities is the Mayor, who is elected by universal suffrage (Law No. 18,695).

The country's decentralized political structure implies that the Ministry of Sport must build links with the different regional and communal administrative institutions. These links aim to develop physical activity and sports at the regional and local levels, in accordance with a state vision (which involves continuously maintaining institutional coordination) based on the guidelines set by public policy in the sports sector.

The Ministry of Sport (MINDEP), in accordance with Article 1 of Law 20.686, is "the highest authority assisting the President of the Republic on matters related to the National Sports Policy." Furthermore, it is responsible for "coordinating sports-related actions carried out by ministries and public services within their respective areas of competence, taking into account the different regional and municipal perspectives in its implementation" (Article 2).

In this regard, the Ministry of Sport works with other Ministries (sectors) to coordinate various management instruments (Policies, Plans, and Programs) in the fields of health (Ministry of Health), education (Ministry of Education), labor (Ministry of Labor), science (Ministry of Science, Technology, Knowledge, and Innovation), among others. These relationships make it possible to determine how each sector can contribute to, coordinate, and/or complement public sports policy by establishing roles based on legal competencies, programmatic scope, government commitments, and available budgets.

Chile has a National Physical Activity and Sports Policy 2016-2025 (2016), whose purpose is to "Promote the comprehensive, individual, and community development of the population, through the systematic practice of physical activity and sport, in its various forms, throughout life, from a rights-based approach that safeguards gender equity, interculturality, and social inclusion in its broadest sense" (p. 111). To achieve this purpose, the policy outlines four objectives:

- Objective 1: Increase the participation of the population at the local, regional, and national levels in the systematic practice of physical activity and sport throughout the entire life course.
- Objective 2: Promote the opportunities, benefits, and values of engaging in physical activity and sport.
- Objective 3: Articulate a National System of Physical Activity and Sport that involves all public and private actors in its development.
- Objective 4: Position Chile in international high-level competition, through the training and improvement of conventional and Paralympic sports performance.

Due to its relevance, the Ministry must evaluate and update the National Policy, redirecting it according to current international instruments and the main challenges of the country in the field of physical activity and sport, to increase the rate of sufficiently active individuals.

As indicated by the global trend, the National Physical Activity and Sport Surveys in Chile (2018) have shown the relationship between a lower socioeconomic level and less participation in physical activity. Similarly, the survey reveals a gender gap, with men generally being more active than women (2018). Consequently, the Ministry of Sport has ensured that public sports policies focus on lower-income areas or those with greater multidimensional vulnerability, aiming to reduce the gaps caused by

socioeconomic conditions. Likewise, the Ministry of Sport has made various efforts to promote the development of women in relation to physical activity and sport in the country.

Considering the above, it is important to consider the role of culture and people's habits, which ultimately shape more or less active lifestyles. MINDEP is aware of this influence and has ensured the creation of policies and interventions that strengthen an active lifestyle, through the dissemination of knowledge and values, as well as the implementation of systematic programmatic offerings that make physical activity a recurring part of everyone's life course.

MINDEP is convinced that promoting physical activity and sport brings benefits to the physical and mental health of our population and is also a valuable tool for the social development of the country, contributing, for example, to issues of security and social cohesion. In this regard, the Ministry is committed to promoting the systematic use of public spaces for physical activity, encouraging the inclusive reconnection of communities through physical, bodily, and sports practices, and fostering the transmission of prosocial values that promote integration and contribute to increasing people's sense of security. Chile is convinced that sport can help build a better society and is determined to enshrine this belief.

Considering that Chile has a solid integration into the international political system, and with the aim of strengthening the reach and impact of its public policies, it has committed to the Sustainable Development Goals (Agenda 2030). In this context, the Ministry of Sport seeks to establish a systemic paradigm, which means that physical activity and sport can be enhanced from various areas of action and generate positive consequences for other sectors of national development. Therefore, its efforts are constantly aimed at fostering smooth intersectoral links to promote coordinated public interventions. Given this, Chile has committed to the Ibero-American Sport Indicators Pilot, as this participation will allow mapping the reality of physical activity and sport in the country, comparing it with the regional reality, collecting international best practices, and guiding national public policies, considering various factors such as: physical activity participation rates, sports institutions, gender gaps, health and physical inactivity, among other variables.

II. Indicator Creation Process

The indicator creation process, from the mandate of the XXVIII CID Assembly in the Dominican Republic for their creation to the presentation of the pilot results at the XXX Assembly in Washington, spans a two-year period of intense work between the countries in the region and the institutions that make up the Consortium responsible for their implementation.

The timeline of the indicator creation process is shown in Figure 1, highlighting the key political, technical, and operational milestones leading up to the presentation of the pilot results.

Figure 1. *Timeline of the Indicator Creation Process*

An important aspect to highlight is that the current set of 12 indicators and four key data points is the result of a broader set of 60 indicators that was used as discussion material in an extensive participatory analysis process in the region. This process included the application of an online exploratory questionnaire with the participation of 83 specialists from different fields; 18 semi-structured interviews with experts from academia, government representatives, and international organizations; two focus groups with 22 government representatives; and a preliminary validation virtual meeting in November 2022. This event involved 37 government representatives from 17 countries in the region. Additionally, technical validation was carried out by the governments of the region during the seminar: “Plan for the creation of sports indicators in sustainable development in Ibero-America,” held in Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia in March 2023.

Based on the above, the implementation of 12 indicators and four key data points was approved at the XXIX General Assembly of the CID in Cartagena, Colombia, as well as the implementation of a pilot program of indicators in a group of applicant countries.

In this way, in June 2023, the Consortium launched a call to the CID countries to participate in the pilot study based on certain basic technical criteria and institutional commitments for the applicant countries. After analyzing the applications, the following month, the interested countries were informed that the pilot, in its first phase of implementation, would include the participation of Chile, Costa Rica, and Ecuador.

III. General Progress Overview

In relation to the results for estimating the value of the indicators, Chile achieved a very positive performance by successfully implementing all four key data points and eight out of the 12 indicators (66.6%). The summary of progress regarding the value of the indicators is shown in Table 1, highlighting some important observations in the third column, which will be addressed in greater detail in the next section.

Table 1. Results of the Implementation of Key Data Points and Indicators in the Pilot

Key Data Point	Value	Observations
1. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes."
2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Ministry	
3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes."
4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Yes	
Indicator	Value	Context
1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	0.62%	
2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	No value	It is necessary to have a satellite account for its calculation.
3. Percentage of the population over 18 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender*	18.7%	Not comparable with the value of other countries.
4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	8.3%	Percentage generated by GOPA.
5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	No value	Necessary to have verified administrative records.
6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	16.5%	
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	0%	
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	52.4%	
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old	42.9%	
10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	No value	
11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	No value	Necessary to have a survey for its calculation.
12. Percentage of government programs in health, sports, and healthy living that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence**	4.3%	

Note: * Chile uses a stricter methodology for estimating its percentage, so it is not strictly comparable with the percentages of Costa Rica and Ecuador.

** The indicator is not strictly comparable between countries because Chile considers the entirety of "social and non-social programs in the health, sport, and life dimension," while Ecuador considers all "projects from the Social Development, Health, and Human Talent cabinets."

IV. Situation of Key Data Points and Indicators

In this section, the situation regarding the value of the key data and indicators is presented, regardless of whether their value was successfully calculated during the pilot phase. For each data point and indicator, a brief justification or relevance for its calculation is provided, as well as its basic characteristics. Additionally, the country's position regarding the status of the indicators is highlighted, alongside the policies or strategic actions being implemented or planned to strengthen compliance with the indicators.

The details for the calculation of the indicators, as well as the concepts used, can be found, for indicators with value, in the technical sheets document for the country; and for indicators without value, in the general guide for the development of technical sheets. The main fields of information contained in the technical sheets are indicator definition, justification, calculation method, unit of measurement, year, periodicity, geographical coverage, information sources, and concepts used, among others.

Key data point I. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.

Key data point with value

To support evidence-based policy and program design for sports and physical activity, it is essential to have representative, reliable, and periodic data. Having a national survey on sports participation and physical activity, disaggregated by gender and age groups, is the first step in building basic indicators in the field, such as the percentage of the population sufficiently active physically and the existing gaps by gender or age groups.

The reference survey to generate information on sports and physical activity in Chile is one of the most comprehensive in the region. However, it is considered to only partially meet the requirements due to its age, as it is more than 5 years old, and it is not representative of the populations under 18 years old, between 18 and 64 years old, and over 65 years old. Additionally, the microdata and basic tabulated results of the survey are not fully available to the public.

Table 2. Basic features of the key data point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	2018	Ministerio del Deporte de Chile (2018)

Country's Positioning

Chile has a wide variety of representative national surveys for the population over 18 years (2016 and 2018), between 5 and 17 years (2019), over 5 years (2021), and with disabilities (2020). In 2024, there will be one for the population under 5 years. Most of these surveys also have representativeness for men and women and for all regions of the country.

However, Chile's challenge is to have a national survey that can measure the entire life course of individuals (i.e., representativeness for the age groups under 17, 18 to 64, and 65 or older), as required to comply with the data.

For this reason, the country aims to implement a National Physical Activity and Sport Survey every 4 years, which will, at a minimum, have representativeness for the age groups 5 to 17 and 18 and older. Additionally, this instrument will have representativeness by sex (male and female), area (urban or rural), and for all regions of the country. In relation to this indicator, the possibility of increasing the representativeness of the population in this survey will be assessed.

Key data point 2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity

Key data point with value

The governmental rank of the national governing body of sport and physical activity determines its ability to establish regulations, design policies, implement programs, and manage resources. Therefore, it is a key data point to establish the scope of the national governing body of sport and physical activity in the country.

It is considered that the most appropriate governmental rank for the national governing body of sport and physical activity should be that of a ministry or an entity with a high degree of autonomy and powers similar to those of a ministry.

The governmental rank of the national governing body for sport and physical activity in Chile is that of a Ministry.

Table 3. Basic features of the key data point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Ministry	2024	Congreso Nacional de Chile (2013)

Country's Positioning

The Ministry of Sport in Chile has the authority to propose and evaluate the National Sports Policy, formulate programs aimed at the development of physical activity and sport, and coordinate with other ministries and public services. Thus, the Ministry is empowered to propose legal or regulatory initiatives, participate in international cooperation programs in sports, and establish collaboration agreements with other entities, whether public or private.

The Ministry was created following the approval and publication of Law No. 20,686 in 2013. Among its functions, it is responsible for proposing and evaluating the National Sports Policy and formulating programs and actions aimed at the development of physical activity and sports for the population, as well as high-performance sports, both conventional and adapted (Art. 2°). It must also coordinate sports-related actions carried out by other Ministries and public services within their respective areas of competence. Additionally, the Ministry is tasked with studying and proposing legal, regulatory, and administrative initiatives that promote and develop physical activity and sports. In the execution of these actions, the Ministry is also responsible for defining strategies to disseminate values, ideals, and knowledge related to physical activity and sport, encouraging the systematic practice of the population.

The Ministry of Sports (MINDEP) includes two institutions, each with independent budgets that are approved annually through the National Budget Law:

- The Undersecretariat of Sports, which designs the national policy on physical activity and sports; and
- The National Institute of Sports, which implements the national policy on physical activity and sports.

The status of the Ministry of Sport allows it to promote the creation of initiatives, policies, and public interventions in the country, granting it autonomy to foster new institutional relationships. To achieve this, the Ministry of Sport has developed an intersectoral approach, managing collaboration agreements with public entities such as the ministries of education, labor, health, and social development, among others, as well as with private entities (for example, in the field of physical and intellectual disabilities). These coordination dynamics enable sports public policies to impact various spheres of social life.

These partnerships aim to develop physical activity and sports from different perspectives. For example, they promote spaces for physical activity and sports within educational institutions, establish physical activity as an important factor in systematically preventing and treating non-communicable diseases within the health sector, and provide social benefits to high-performance athletes to support their sports careers, among other actions.

Key data point 3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.

Key data point with value

"Each education system must assign the requisite place and importance to physical education, physical activity and sport in order to establish a balance and strengthen links between physical activities and other components of education. It must also ensure that quality and inclusive physical education classes are included, preferentially on a daily basis." (UNESCO, 2015a, p. 3).

Thus, there is a need for data or indicators that allow us to assess countries' commitment to promoting physical education in early childhood—a stage that, as widely documented, is critical for shaping habits and lifestyles in adulthood.

In Chile's curriculum, the related subject is called "Physical Education and Health." However, it is unclear whether physical education is an independent subject from health. Additionally, the curriculum does not explicitly specify the number of hours per week allocated to the subject. For these reasons, Chile's compliance with the key data point value is considered partial.

Table 4. Basic features of the key data point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	2024	Ministerio de Educación de Chile (2023)

Country's Positioning

Chile organizes much of its educational content based on the "National Curriculum Guidelines" (Currículum Nacional, 2024). These guidelines state that in basic (or primary) education, "Physical Education and Health" is a mandatory subject within the curriculum. However, in the curriculum guidelines for the final cycle of secondary education (third and fourth years of high school), "Physical Education and Health" is part of the General Elective Education Plan, meaning it is not mandatory.

According to the National Curriculum Guidelines, Chile allocates 4 hours per week for Physical Education and Health from 1st to 4th grade (with students approximately between 5 and 10 years old) and 2 hours per week from 5th grade to 12th grade (with students approximately between 11 and 17 years old). In practice, this generally translates to two classes per week for the younger students and one class per week for older students.

It is important to note that the physical activity and sports practiced by students—and by children and adolescents in general—should not be addressed solely through a strategy that establishes a mandatory physical activity subject. Therefore, it is crucial to review the structure of school schedules to determine whether they contribute to promoting active and healthy habits. Additionally, analyzing the factors that limit the time available for motor activities is essential. Most importantly, it is vital to seek alternatives that allow the use of other times and spaces for physical activity both within and beyond educational institutions, extending beyond the designated subject. In this regard, the Ministry of Sport reaffirms its commitment to continuously seeking new strategies that promote physical activity and sports participation during school years.

Key data point 4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.

Key data point with value

Legal frameworks are particularly relevant because they express fundamental principles and rights of individuals, as well as the priorities and scope of objectives, strategies, and programs. This highlights the importance of having data on the existence of legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.

To establish the existence of such legal frameworks and ensure that they are effectively being applied, it is necessary to present evidence that the legal instruments have been used to design policies, programs, or actions with concrete results to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.

The value regarding the existence of legal frameworks in Chile is positive, as the country has a General Protocol for the prevention and sanctioning of sexual harassment, sexual abuse, discrimination, and mistreatment in national sports activities. This protocol was approved and published through Supreme Decree No. 22 in 2020, and evidence has been presented showing that it has indeed been applied.

Table 5. Basic features of the key data point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Yes	2024	Ministerio del Deporte de Chile (2020)

Country's Positioning

The Protocol must be implemented within all sports organizations, which, depending on their size, must have (or not) a person in charge of ensuring compliance with the Protocol. In this regard, for example, the Professional Football Sports Organization "Club Deportivo Universidad Católica" implements and disseminates the Protocol, creating reporting mechanisms and an institutional responsible person who ensures compliance with the regulations, as well as receiving and guiding complaints. Similarly, the National Sports Institute also implements the Protocol as part of its Programmatic Offer, defining Institutional Responsible People for the main sports facilities it manages, and publishes this information on its website.

To further improve this protocol, which is consistent with the Ministry of Sport's commitment to strengthening gender equality and preventing discriminatory behaviors or violations in the sports field, the possibility of enhancing the content of the protocol will be analyzed in 2024. To achieve this, it is necessary to conduct an evaluation that allows for the identification of strengths and weaknesses as seen by the various stakeholders involved, such as athletes, sports organizations, and academic communities.

Indicator I. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity

Indicator with value

The allocation of the budget to sports and physical activity is an objective measure of the importance given to the sector in public investment priorities, and at the same time, a concrete reference regarding the scope of policies in terms of available resources.

A limitation of the indicator is that it does not record the budget for sports and physical activity allocated to government offices outside the national governing entity in the field. Therefore, it is desirable that in the future, a broader indicator be developed to more accurately capture the number of public resources allocated to the sector.

The percentage of the public budget in Chile allocated to the national governing entity for sports and physical activity, that is, the Ministry of Sport, was 0.62% in 2023. However, as explained later, this year the budget was significantly higher than the usual percentage allocated due to Chile's responsibility in organizing the 2023 Pan American and Parapan American Games in Santiago de Chile.

Table 6. Basic features of the indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	0.62% Equivalent to 79,085,123,721 Chilean pesos	2023	Ministerio de Hacienda de Chile (2022)

Country's Positioning

Chile annually approves its budget for the public sector through a law. Law No. 21.516, dated December 20, 2022, approves the "Budgets for the Public Sector 2023".

The main difficulty faced by the country in calculating the indicator regarding the public budget invested in the national entity for sports and physical activity (MINDEP-IND) is that, during the observed year 2023, Chile hosted the Pan American and Parapan American Games in Santiago 2023, which required additional financial resources for their execution. Normally, the annual budget of the entity corresponds to 20% of what was allocated during the year 2023.

Indicator 2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP

Indicator without value

Sports and physical activity have a significant impact on multiple sectors and economic activities, but due to the lack of measurements or information records, this impact has not been adequately recognized or valued. Therefore, having statistics on the contribution of sports and physical activity to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) would help highlight their impact, understand their relationship with other sectors or economic activities, and also support the design of policies and programs.

However, having this indicator presents considerable challenges for countries due to the technical complexity of its calculation and the financial needs to create its information sources. The ideal source of information for the indicator is a satellite account for sports and physical activity, as it provides precision and allows for a proper breakdown of the main economic sectors or activities related to sports and physical activity.

Table 7. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

In Chile, the monetary value of goods and services related to sports and physical activity produced during a period is not specifically accounted for. Instead, the indicator calculated by Chile is broader, as it calculates economic activity based on general industries such as fishing, agriculture-forestry, mining, manufacturing, commerce, transportation, construction, among others. It is important to consider that the development of sports and the sports industry goes beyond the contribution made by public management and state institutions. Therefore, the measurement of this indicator should be constructed at both the public and private levels, considering the contribution of sports in various spheres, such as the economy, construction, or transportation.

Indicator 3. Percentage of the population over 18 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender

Indicator with value

Regular physical activity is one of the most important mechanisms for the prevention and treatment of non-communicable diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, and several types of cancer. Physical activity is also beneficial for mental health, as it prevents cognitive decline and symptoms of depression and anxiety (WHO, 2020). Therefore, it is crucial to have indicators on the percentages of the population that are sufficiently physically active.

Simultaneously, given the different needs of individuals and the existing inequalities among them, it is important to break down the indicators by age, sex or gender, ethnic origin, or socioeconomic status, among other factors. This allows for the visibility of inequalities and inclusion challenges for sports and physical activity policies.

For the indicator value presented by Chile, it is important to make a clarification. This is because Chile's percentage is considerably different from that of Costa Rica and Ecuador, which may partly be explained by the profile of their populations, but also by differences in the questionnaire used. However, since it was not possible to access the specific questionnaire used by Costa Rica and Ecuador (Chile did provide it), nor the microdata resulting from the data collection (none of the countries have them available directly to the public), it is not possible to know for sure. Without a doubt, this represents one of the major areas of opportunity to have indicators that, while based on national definitions, also have a consistent concept and calculation method across the region.

Table 8. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the population over 18 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	18.7%	2018	Ministerio del Deporte de Chile (2018)

Country's Positioning

The indicator was calculated using the database from the 2018 Survey (National Survey of Physical Activity and Sports Habits 2018 in the Population Aged 18 and Over). The main challenge identified is that the databases of the National Surveys are not published on official websites. Therefore, for the public to access these databases, they must make a request to the Ministry (through Law 20.285 on Access to Public Information).

A management proposal is being assessed to allow the publication, in the proactive transparency section of the institutional website, of information from upcoming National Surveys on physical activity and sports conducted by the Ministry. This would include their anonymized databases, as well as methodological and results reports.

The calculation of the sufficiently active population is based on the following: Physically Active according to the WHO refers to individuals who engage in physical activity or sports according to WHO recommendations, which is 150 minutes per week of moderate-intensity physical activity or 75 minutes per week of vigorous-intensity physical activity. On the other hand, Physically Inactive according to the WHO refers to individuals who engage in physical activity or sports without meeting the WHO recommendations or do not engage in any physical activity.

Indicator 4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old

Indicator with value

According to the WHO (2022), "Physical inactivity is one of the leading risk factors for noncommunicable diseases mortality. People who are insufficiently active have a 20% to 30% increased risk of death compared to people who are sufficiently active."

Therefore, it becomes essential to have indicators on deaths related to physical inactivity that allow quantifying the magnitude of the problem for each country, and from this, implement policies to address it.

Table 9. Basic features of the indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	8.3%	2021	Global Observatory for Physical Activity (2021)

Country's Positioning

The last calculation for this indicator was performed in 2018 by the Global Observatory for Physical Activity (GOPA). However, it cannot be assured that this organization will continue to calculate this indicator in the future. For this reason, the Ministry of Sport will assess the possibility of exploring a collaboration agreement with the Ministry of Health and the Civil Registry to establish formal mechanisms for data sharing. This would enable the country to autonomously calculate, through the management of the Ministry of Sport, the number of deaths caused by physical inactivity among the population over 18 years old, incorporating variables such as gender.

Indicator 5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education

Indicator without value

"Physical education is the most effective means of providing all children and youth with the skills, attitudes, values, knowledge and understanding for lifelong participation in society" (UNESCO, 2015b, p. 6).

Due to the previous reasons, it is important to know the percentage of primary and secondary schools that provide the minimum number of minutes of physical education. To have a reliable indicator, it is desirable that this be the result of a school census or, if not possible, a representative survey. For Chile, there is currently not enough information to establish the value of the indicator.

Table 10. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

Currently, the subject related to physical education in Chile is called "Physical Education and Health" according to the National Curriculum (2024). Although the inclusion of the health aspect is done through physical activity, that is, by conveying content related to an active and healthy lifestyle, there is a possibility that not all minutes of the subject are dedicated exclusively to movement. In this scenario, there is not enough evidence to accurately determine the weekly minutes of physical education practiced in the country's schools.

The National Curriculum is implemented throughout the country by educational institutions, which establishes the minimum number of hours that must be dedicated to each subject according to the level of education. However, the Ministry of Sport will evaluate the feasibility of having a statistical mechanism to measure, in practice, how many minutes, on average, are dedicated to physical activity and sports per educational institution. Notwithstanding the above, the Ministry of Sport is committed to developing policies and initiatives for physical activity and sports that deepen their practice both within and outside the educational space, as it is aware of the importance of early intervention in fostering a movement culture and a healthy lifestyle.

Indicator 6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender

Indicator with value

The effectiveness of policies for sports and physical activity in education should ultimately be reflected in the proportion of sufficiently active students, especially at the basic education level, as this is where important lifelong habits are formed. This underscores the importance of having such an indicator. Additionally, it is crucial to break down the indicator by gender, as female students have historically faced greater setbacks compared to their male peers in various aspects of development, including sports and physical activity.

Table 11. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	16.5%	2019	Ministerio del Deporte de Chile (2019) Sistema de Información de Tendencias Educativas en América Latina (2019)

Country's Positioning

The main difficulty identified is that the National Surveys and other instruments do not measure this variable considering the WHO definitions (sufficiently physically active or inactive) and the representativeness of the student population in the country. However, the National Physical Activity and Sports Survey for children aged 5 to 17 (2019) allows for mapping a population that is consistent with the student population, as almost all individuals between the ages of 5 and 17 are students. This statement is possible because, according to the Country Profile prepared by SITEAL (2019), in Chile, 99.5% of the population between the ages of 6 and 11 is enrolled in school (p. 5), while 99.5% of the population between 12 and 14 remains stable in the educational system (p. 6); also, 95.5% of the population between 15 and 17 attends educational institutions.

Given that the calculation of this indicator had to be made by working with the databases from the survey, as a challenge, the Ministry of Sport intends to make the databases, statistical reports, and methodological documents of the National Surveys available on the official website. Currently, these files are not published, so for the public to access them, they must submit a request to the Service (through Law 20.285 on Access to Public Information).

Indicator 7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs

Indicator with value

In the budgets of public entities and their objectives, the political and programmatic priorities of the government are reflected, and therefore, they constitute an objective measure to assess the government's efforts to close the gender gaps in sports and physical activity.

To establish the proportion of the budget focused on gender-specific programs, it is necessary for these programs to have explicit and verifiable objectives and actions aimed at closing the gender gaps.

Table 12. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	0%	2023	Ministerio de Hacienda de Chile (2022)

Country's Positioning

The Ministry of Sport does not have exclusive government programs to address gender issues. As a result, it was not possible to define the budget that this entity focuses on gender-specific programs. However, it is important to highlight that the Ministry implements various targeting strategies within its government programs, which allow for actions aimed at reducing the gender gap in physical activity and sports. For example, the Ministry offers systematic physical activity and sports workshops exclusively for women, provides specific funding for the development of women's football, and offers support to seasonal agricultural workers ("temporeras") through physical activity workshops for their children and adolescents.

Indicator 8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity

Indicator with value

In leadership positions within public or private organizations, one of the most significant gaps between women and men is observed. This highlights the importance of monitoring the situation and progress towards gender equality in leadership roles within national entities for sports and physical activity. Based on this information, it will be possible to support better policies or affirmative actions in this area.

Table 13. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	52.4%	2024	Ministerio del Deporte de Chile e Instituto Nacional de Deporte de Chile (2024)

Country's Positioning

The indicator was not previously calculated by the Ministry of Sport, which meant that the existing organizational structure had to be analyzed, identifying the number of leadership positions and determining the number of men and women holding those positions. Therefore, to meet the indicator, the Ministry of Sport had to prepare a report, which was published on the Transparency ProActiva website corresponding to the Ministry of Sport, allowing public access to this information.

To continue reporting this indicator, and with the intention of developing new reports and indicators that allow for characterizing the gender gap within the institutional framework of the Ministry of Sport, MINDEP will periodically publish updates to this Report.

Indicator 9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old

Indicator with value

There are notable differences in the level of physical activity between women and men, particularly, "the data shows that in almost all countries, girls and women are less active than boys and men" (WHO, 2020, p. 2). In fact, it can also be observed in most countries in the region that the gender gaps increase significantly with age.

One of the most important objectives of sustainable development is to eliminate gender gaps or differences in their multiple dimensions. Therefore, it is crucial that governments and the general public have indicators that allow them to monitor their progress toward reducing or eliminating gender gaps in physical activity between men and women.

Table 14. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old	42.9%	2018	Ministerio del Deporte de Chile (2018)

Country's Positioning

The indicator was constructed based on the database of the National Physical Activity and Sports Survey for the population over 18 years old (2018). In the future, it is considered important that the studies of the Ministry of Sport allow for mapping and characterizing the gender gap regarding physical activity and sports participation (for example, in 2023, the National Survey for children under 5 years old specifically includes the preparation of a Gender Report based on the results obtained).

Consequently, the aim will be for future Final Reports of the National Surveys to specifically outline the gender gap concerning the sufficiently active population. Similarly, the Ministry of Sport is focused on advancing the characterization of the gender gap (beyond the gap in the percentage of sufficiently active population), incorporating other variables that allow for differentiation, such as barriers to access to physical activity and sports participation.

Indicator 10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities

Indicator without value

The Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities establishes that, in order for people with disabilities to participate on an equal footing in recreational, leisure, and sports activities, countries must adopt measures to encourage and promote the participation of people with disabilities in sports activities, ensure they have the opportunity to organize and develop sports and recreational activities, and guarantee their access to sports facilities (UN, 2008).

To put into practice what is established in the Convention, it is necessary to allocate public funds to programs aimed at enabling people with disabilities to access sports and physical activity. Similarly, it is essential to invest in data and indicators with the purpose of measuring whether this objective is being achieved.

Table 15. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

The Ministry of Sport does not have government programs specifically targeted at people with disabilities. As a result, it was not possible to define the budget of this entity that is focused on programs for people with disabilities. However, it is important to highlight that the Ministry implements various targeting strategies within its government programs, which benefit people with disabilities, depending on the objectives of each social program. For example, support is provided for the development of the athletic careers of athletes with disabilities, funding is given to the Chilean Paralympic Committee, national competition spaces for Paralympic athletes are created, and sports projects or research related to people with disabilities are funded, among other strategies. All of these are carried out within the framework of government programs that are not exclusive to people with disabilities but contribute to the development of this population.

Indicator II. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population

Indicator without value

People with disabilities are one of the population groups with the greatest delay in access to development under equal circumstances. For this reason, the way to verify whether policies or programs aimed at the population with disabilities are effectively achieving results is to observe whether their physical activity and sports gaps compared to the rest of the population are decreasing.

To achieve this, it is necessary to have representative surveys on the physical activity levels of the population with disabilities, with disaggregation by age, sex, or gender.

Table 16. *Basic features of the indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

The National Physical Activity and Sports Survey for the population with disabilities only considers representativeness for the population with disabilities over 13 years old. Therefore, there is no instrument (National Survey) that measures physical activity and sports participation considering the representativeness of the population without disabilities. In addition, it is not possible to calculate the indicator, as there is no statistical basis to compare the levels of physical activity and sports participation between the population with disabilities and the population without disabilities.

For Chile to have reliable statistical information to report this indicator, a cycle of National Surveys has been planned, which will generate a National Physical Activity and Sports Survey for the population over 5 years old every 4 years. Within this 4-year periodic cycle, the possibility of a new version of the National Survey for the population with disabilities will be evaluated, with the goal of mapping this indicator and other relevant variables. To achieve this, the feasibility of strengthening the methodology and increasing representativeness will be analyzed, considering disaggregation by sex and region. This will be a valuable statistical input for the country, as it will allow for comparisons of the frequency and characteristics of physical activity and sports participation, depending on the presence (or absence) of disability.

Indicator I2. Percentage of government programs in health, sports, and healthy living that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence

Indicator with value

Sports overcome geographical, social, and political barriers; connect people, communities, and countries; and in this way, promote coexistence and social and political inclusion.

Sport for development and peace is conceived as a social intervention strategy that, using games, physical activity, and sports, addresses explicit objectives of peace and development. This perspective "incorporates issues such as gender equality, the promotion of peaceful coexistence, fostering tolerance for differences, encouraging inclusive behaviors, conflict prevention, and promoting health and well-being" (GIZ, 2021).

For this reason, the relevance of generating indicators on related topics is clear, but at the same time, it presents a challenge for countries due to the technical complexity involved in designing reliable, accurate, and transparent indicators.

Table 17. Basic features of the indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of government programs in health, sports, and healthy living that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	4.3%	2022	Ministerio de Desarrollo Social y Familia de Chile (2024)

Country's Positioning

There are government programs that, although their strategies do not explicitly state that they use sport as a tool for peace and coexistence, in practice, they do (such as the programs of the Ministry of Sport, which promote coexistence and social cohesion in practice through the transmission of values and teamwork dynamics). Consequently, it is not possible to track with complete certainty the number of government programs that, in practice, effectively use sport to promote peace and coexistence (since only those programs that explicitly declare the relationship between sport and peace were able to be identified). In the future, it is expected that at least the government programs associated with the Ministry of Sport, which use physical activity and sport as tools for development and social cohesion, will explicitly declare that their intervention strategies contribute to promoting peace and coexistence. Furthermore, it will be sought to ensure that, in practice, these programs have a clearly defined strategy to achieve this contribution.

V. Lessons learned

As a result of the pilot study, some of the most relevant lessons learned are as follows:

- The implementation of the indicators requires strong political commitment from the countries and institutions that make up the international cooperation consortium, but also from trained technical teams with available human resources and time for the execution of the pilot study.
- The generation of indicators and the creation of their information sources requires having multidisciplinary and intersectoral teams, which, in addition to ensuring the conditions for calculating and monitoring the indicators, would also imply an increase in the capacity of the sports sector to generate data and indicators to support policies and evaluate achievements and outcomes.
- The measurement and monitoring capabilities of government policies can be significantly improved through partnerships with academia or specialized research centers. In addition to their benefits for knowledge generation, such partnerships ensure continuity in the generation of information and the monitoring of indicators.
- Having reliable, periodic, and relevant information and indicators requires investment from both governments and society as a whole. Specifically, for the calculation of some indicators, it is necessary to allocate budget resources for the creation of new representative surveys, censuses, or administrative records, as well as to develop capabilities for data collection, monitoring, and evaluation.

VI. Recommendations and Next Steps

With the objective of implementing all Ibero-American indicators and continue strengthening the country's measurement and information generation capabilities to design evidence-based policies, the following recommendations are made:

- Formation of an interdisciplinary and intersectoral working group (sport, health, economy, national statistics) for mapping information sources and indicators on sport and its impact on development, as well as to propose policies and technical criteria for the generation of statistical information in the field.
- Establish a work plan to generate the indicators that could not be calculated during the pilot. The work plan should include strategies for identifying and, if necessary, creating primary information sources.
- Design a strategy for the monitoring and follow-up of the indicators, which, in addition to implementing the baseline for all the indicators, should include an initial follow-up report to observe the evolution of the indicators. The strategy should also include preliminary targets for the indicators.
- Establish a working mechanism with a local university for the joint development of the indicators.
- Promote international cooperation mechanisms to share experiences, knowledge, and training.
- Seek alliances with financial institutions or international investment funds focused on highlighting inclusion gaps in access to sport and the development of women, people with disabilities, indigenous populations, and people in poverty through reliable indicators and statistical information.
- Invest heavily in the training of human resources for the generation of indicators and monitoring and evaluation systems on the impact of sport on development.

Conclusions

The implementation of the pilot indicators in Chile is considered a success, as the results achieved exceeded the initial expectations set at the beginning of the process. Notably, Chile was able to calculate the value of the four key data points and eight of the 12 indicators that make up the Ibero-American indicator set.

The pilot study has been a valuable exercise, allowing for the mapping of information, identification of challenges, identification of opportunities, and preparation of work teams for the general implementation of the indicators in the near future. At the same time, the lessons learned during the process will allow participating countries in the second phase of the pilot, as well as Chile, to move more quickly in implementing the remaining indicators.

On the other hand, the pilot study has facilitated the collaboration of various sports and physical activity specialists in Chile and the region, which could lead to broader bilateral and multilateral cooperation projects, strengthening knowledge transfer in Ibero-America on measurements and the generation of indicators to evaluate achievements and results of policies.

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